

TEACHING FACULTY PERSPECTIVE: SERVANT LEADERSHIP'S ROLE IN UNIVERSITY JOB SATISFACTION

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15074329>

Keywords

Job Satisfaction, Servant Leadership, Universities, Altruistic Calling, Wisdom.

Article History

Received on 22 January 2025
Accepted on 22 February 2025
Published on 11 March 2025

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Abstract

Servant leadership has grown exponentially in recent years, turning into acceptable model for organizations and employees' to search for honesty, humility, credibility, empowerment, social responsibility, information sharing, paying attention to spiritual and moral and so on. This study focuses on academic faculty in universities. This study identified five imperative factors of servant leadership affecting the faculty satisfaction on job: altruistic calling, emotional healing, persuasive mapping, wisdom and organizational stewardship. The study was conducted in universities of Peshawar by taking 300 faculty members as sample size. A structured questionnaire survey was conducted by taking a cross sectional research design under probability sampling and total of 270 questionnaires were obtained. This study proved that, servant leadership has positive relation with job satisfaction. The results supported the suppositions of the study.

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INTRODUCTION

Employee job satisfaction has always been an issue and still it is the most difficult problem for organizations as to how they can improve employees' satisfaction to enhance organizational performance. Several researches have been conducted to solve the problem, and among the findings was one about improving leadership style that is a key perspective (Ingram, Lafarge, Locander, Mackenzie, and Podsakoff, 2005). Researches have proved that job satisfaction mainly based on quality of relationship. A leader also plays a dominant role in higher educational institutions. Those leaders who cultivate pleasant relationship by promoting career development will effectively enhance job satisfaction (Ding, Lu, Song & Lu, 2012). Servant leadership helps to create positive working environment, enhancing workers sense of belonging, job

satisfaction and loyalty to the organization (Ding, Lu, Song & Lu, 2012). The traditional leadership style in Pakistan universities is authoritarian, which demonstrates a superior leadership style. In fact, staff-oriented style of leadership brings employees' job satisfaction and increase work quality of the organizations. Most studies revealed that employees leave the organization when they feel that they are dissatisfied with their supervisors and they cannot be trusted (Ali & Hussain, 2012; Bryant, 2003; Contee-Borders, 2002; Dennis and Winston, 2003; Patterson, 2003; Laub, 2003; Drury, 2005; Dennis and Bocarnea, 2005; Greenleaf and Spears, 1998; Ding, Lu, Song & Lu, 2012). Several leadership models and styles available, however in the last few years servant leadership model was under discussion. Leadership styles have been investigated in Pakistan

background, but servant leadership is still an unnoticed area in this perspective. Majority of the studies on servant leadership have centered on western culture so keep in mind the diversity of cultures and it is a good justification to study servant leadership model in the Pakistani context to know it's possible attitudinal consequences (Ali & Hussain, 2012).

Literature Review

Servant leadership

This model was first introduced by Greenleaf in 1977. Servant leadership; it is based on the idea of a servant as the leader. Servant leadership was a new model for leadership, serving others is the core precedence of a servant leader (Spears, 2005). True leader must consider himself as a servant for his followers, and this aspiration to serve, makes a great leader (Rimes,2011). The main characteristics of servant leaders stressed are to empower subordinates, personal development, and put the interest of those who are being led before the interest of the leader. Servant leadership is a realistic philosophy of leadership that supports teamwork, advances service, and develops trust, willingness to listen to others and future orientation. (Rimes, 2011; Greenleaf,1977). The concept of servant leader is behind the spiritual leader, it shows full and highest commitment to workers (Ding, Lu, Song & Lu, 2012). Transformational leadership motivates employees' to achieve goals while servant leadership is to serve staff. Researchers put forward their own frameworks to measure servant leadership. Among the most recent studies, Barbuto & Wheeler (2006) developed five dimensional model, they are; altruistic calling, emotional healing, wisdom, persuasive mapping, organizational stewardship. Seven dimensional model of Patterson, (2003) they are; agapao Love, humility, altruism, vision, trust, empowering others, service. Van (2011) provided eight dimensional model, they are; humility, authenticity, forgiveness, empowerment, accountability standing back, courage and stewardship Laub (1998) proposed a six dimensional model of servant leadership; they are; value people, authenticity, develop people, build communities, provide leadership and share leadership. Page & Wong (2000) eleven dimensional model, they are; integrity, humility, goal setting,

servant hood, developing others, empowering others caring for others, visioning, leading, team building, shared decision making Buchen (1998) proposed four facets model of servant leadership, they are; self identity, capacity for reciprocity (mutual dependence), relationship building, preoccupation with future. . Greenleaf and Spears (1998) presented eleven dimensional model, they are; empathy, healing, awareness, listening, persuasion, conceptualization, stewardship, building communities foresight, commitment to growth of others. Farling, Stone and Winston (1999) suggested five dimensional model, they are; vision, credibility, trust, influence and Service.

Dimensions of Servant Leadership

In this study the researcher has adopted Barbuto & Wheeler (2006) five dimensional model to measure servant leadership, they are; altruistic calling, emotional healing, wisdom, persuasive mapping, organizational stewardship. Altruistic calling, this facet of servant leadership measure the level of intentional and voluntary actions that aims to enhance the welfare of other persons (McCann, Graves and Cox,2014). Different researches showed impact on job satisfaction (Barbuto & Wheeler, 2006; McCann, et al., 2014). Emotional healing as mentioned by Barbuto & Wheeler (2006) and McCann, Graves and Cox (2014) is the characteristic of servant leader that foster healing process and recovery of employee's from hardship and trauma out and out. McCann, Graves and Cox (2014) also carried a study which showed this behavior of leader played significant role in ones job satisfaction. Wisdom can be defined the ability of leader in terms of awareness from environment, using of sense to make quality decision which of the mark. Recognize problems and nip the evils on the bud. (Sosik & Megerian,1999; Sternberg, 2003). Barbuto & Wheeler (2006) identified this behavior of leader play a key role in worker job satisfaction. Persuasive Mapping as mentioned by Barbuto & Wheeler (2006) this ability motivate employees towards their goals and ambitions by developing and encouraging logical thinking in employees. Organizational Stewardship is the ability of the leader to think about the social responsibility of the organization. Prepare and motivate organization to develop programs for

serving community and society. (Searle & Barbuto, 2010).

Servant Leadership and Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction maybe defined as it fits between what the organization requires and what the employee is seeking and actually receiving. It is the internal feeling of a person regarding achievement that may be qualitative or quantitative. It is affected by culture and management style, empowerment employee involvement and autonomous work of groups. Job satisfaction is an affirmative and happy emotional condition which one realizes from ones value (Ding,etal., 2012; Ilies & Judge,2004).Anderson(2005) also identified from his study that there was correlation between servant leadership and job satisfaction. The authors mentioned below have mentioned in their studies regarding servant leadership impact on job satisfaction, job satisfaction impact with loyalty and organizational performance. They have also mentioned that the behavior of servant leadership increased job satisfaction (Babin, Lee, Kim & Griffin 2005; Jones, Reynold & Arnold, 2006; Wright & Bonett, 2007; Jenkins & Stewart 2008; Lisbijanto & Budiyanto, 2014). Based on the above available literature the research assumptions are given under.

- H1.**There is significant relationship between altruistic calling and job Satisfaction
- H2.**There is significant relationship between emotional healing and job satisfaction
- H3.**There is significant relationship between wisdom and job satisfaction
- H4.**There is significant relationship between persuasive Mapping and job satisfaction
- H5.**There is significant relationship between organizational stewardship and job satisfaction.

Research Methodology

Target respondents

The object of this research was to check the impact of servant leadership on job satisfaction .In order to achieve the anticipated objective a study was conducted in universities of Peshawar. For this study the target respondents were faculty in universities of Peshawar. Survey conducted through structured questionnaire. Total 250 questionnaires were

distributed in different universities with return rate 83%. The reliability of the measurement checked through cronbach’s alpha.

Measurement

A structured questionnaire was used to collect the data. The questionnaire was divided into two parts: demographic and research variables. All items were adopted from previous researches: twenty three items from Barbuto and Wheeler (2006) servant leadership Measurement; 18 items from Weiss, et al. (1967) for job satisfaction. Before data collection all the questionnaire was sent for expert review. Two hundred and eight questionnaires were collected during the research survey.

Data analysis and discussion

Respondent profile

All respondents in this study were faculty members aged between 22 and 60 years. Majority of the respondents were well qualified: master 53, PhD 56, M.phil 81. Respondent male and female ratio was: male 144 and female 64. Respondents from public sector were 108 and from private sector were 100. In terms of position: professor 20, associates professor 25, assistant professor 68, lecturers 80 and junior lecturer 15.

Reliability

Individual reliability of the scale was measured through Cronbach’s alpha and showed sufficient level of internal consistency. All the values were higher than .70, the reliability of servant leadership for 23 items was .873, and for 18 items of job satisfaction were .804, implying that all the constructs in measurement was reliable.

Hypothesis testing:

Multiple regressions were employed to identify the relationship between endogenous and exogenous variable. Results are shown in table 1. The outcome shows that R-square was 0.404, which exhibits that independent variable elucidates 40.4% of the variance in job satisfaction. The linear relation between altruistic calling, emotional healing, wisdom, persuasive mapping and organizational stewardship with job satisfaction is significant with F-value of 76.795 at the .000 significance level. Thus the model fits this study.

H1. There is significant relationship between altruistic calling and job Satisfaction
 Since the significance level of altruistic calling with job satisfaction was.000 which is less than 0.05, Hence H1 is accepted. Altruistic calling was the highest coefficient (beta=0.319), therefore, altruistic calling is significant positive relationship with job satisfaction.

H2. There is significant relationship between emotional healing and job satisfaction Significance level of emotional healing with job satisfaction was 0.475 being greater than 0.05, Hence H2 is rejected. Emotional healing was the lowest coefficient (beta=0.049). Hence H2 is rejected..

H3. There is significant relationship between wisdom and job satisfaction
 The significance level of wisdom with job satisfaction as shown in table 1 was 0.000 which is less than 0.05,

Hence H3 is accepted. Wisdom was the second highest coefficient (beta=0.258). Hence, wisdom is significant positive relationship with job satisfaction

H4. There is significant relationship between persuasive Mapping and job satisfaction According to results shown in table1, persuasive mapping did not have a significant relationship with job satisfaction due to the significant level (0.329) being greater than 0.05. Hence H4 is rejected.

H5. There is significant relationship between organizational stewardship and job satisfaction
 The significance level of organizational stewardship with job satisfaction as shown is table 1 was 0.001 which is less than 0.05. Hence H5 is accepted. Organizational stewardship was the third highest coefficient (beta=0.177). Hence, organizational stewardship is significant relationship with job satisfaction.

Table 1: Multiple Linear Regressions
Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

	Un-standardized coefficient		standardized coefficients		t	Sig
	Beta	Std. error	Beta			
Altruistic Calling	0.212	0.035	0.319		6.097	0.000
Emotional Healing	0.034	0.048	0.049		0.715	0.475
Wisdom	0.199	0.05	0.258		4.008	0.000
Persuasive Mapping	0.034	0.035	0.055		0.978	0.329
Organizational Stewardship	0.14	0.042	0.177		3.305	0.001

R=.636, R2=.404, F=76.795 Sig=.000

Discussion

Altruistic calling: According to Patterson (2003) altruism is the key antecedent that directly impact employees’ job satisfaction. Altruistic calling behavior of servant leadership helps of fulfilling employees’ needs of empathy and creates superior level of employees’ loyalty and satisfaction towards particular organization. (Carter, 2012; Rimes, 2011; Vondey, 2010; McCann, et al., 2014). Hence, having this ability by the servant leader is critical for educational institutions to attract more qualified faculties and increase universities performance.

Emotional Healing: The result of this study with regards emotional healing is not consistent with preceding findings. Emotional healing is the ability

of servant leader to recover employees’ from shock and distress. According to this study finding, most faculty members are not concerned with emotional healing behavior of servant leadership in universities. This study did not support previous studies such as Barbuto & Wheeler (2008), McCann, et al. (2014) and Liden, Wayne, Zhao & Herderson (2008).

Wisdom: The results of this study regarding wisdom supported by Greenleaf & Spears (1998), Russell & Stone(2002), Patterson (2003), Barbuto & Wheeler (2008) and McCann, et al. (2014)

They indicated that wisdom played an important role in servant leadership behavior. According to Liden, Wayne, Zhao & Herderson (2008), if a servant leader has this ability it will make employees’ enthusiastic to

trust on leader. In addition, McCann et al. (2014) research also found that supposed lack of wisdom was one of the reasons why employees distrust the leader and thus, perturb the growth of organization.

Persuasive mapping :The result of this study with regards persuasive mapping is not consistent with previous studies. Persuasive mapping is the ability of servant leader to develop sense of logical thinking and motivate employees' towards attainment of goals. According to findings, most faculty members are not concerned with persuasive mapping behavior of servant leadership in universities. But this study supported the results of Van (2011), Northouse (2015) and Sendjaya, Sarros & Santora (2008).

Organizational stewardship

In the study of Van (2011) and McCann, et al. (2014), organizational stewardship behavior of servant leadership was considered prominent indicator for organizational performance and employees' satisfaction. Organizational stewardship can be defined as how much organization is responsible for society and community to provide them better services. This ability enhances employees' trust and contributing to competitive advantage for organization. Thus, this ability of the leader in university may help to gain competitive advantage over other competitors. Greenleaf & Spears (1998), Russell & Stone (2002), Luab (2002) ,Barbuto & Wheeler (2006), and Northouse (2015) have also discovered that organizational stewardship can be influential in satisfying employees' and retaining employees' loyalty.

Conclusion

This study focused on the leadership problem faced by universities in Peshawar, Pakistan. Overall, five hypotheses in relation to altruistic calling, emotional healing, wisdom, persuasive mapping and organizational stewardship were developed. With a sample of 208 faculty members' participants, the findings of regression test showed that all variables, excluding emotional healing and persuasive mapping, were significant predictors of employees' job satisfaction.

Implications

As indicated in the findings, there is significant relationship between altruistic calling, wisdom, organizational stewardship and job satisfaction. Therefore, the universities leaders should further improve altruistic calling, wisdom and organizational stewardship behavior to satisfy faculty members. Universities administration should design and arrange specialcourses and training sessions on servant leadership to educate further their managerial staff (Carter, 2012; Rimes, 2011). Furthermore, the universities should also keep courses and training contents on servant leadership clear and simple. Not only will this give their managerial staff with more information about servant leadership, university priorities and services but also help bond their relationship with faculty members and students.

The universities should also take action to improve their decision making powers by developing logical reasoning skills in managerial staff. No well qualified individual will join there if they feel career insecure as to the leader wisdom ability. In short, strong and improve wisdom ability could create faculty trust and ability to build long term relationship with management. Hence this would increase faculty job satisfaction and low intention to quit in a particular university.

Nowadays, organizational stewardship or social responsibility has become indispensable in satisfying employees' and general public. Universities are strongly advised to provide superior services and benefits to society and faculty members, such as quality education ,prompt services response to student's parent's complaint and request, seminars and training programs for faculty members, social awareness to serve for community. If the university is unable to provide real time services it may create doubts. Most important, a university leader should maintain the quality of stewardship because a good leader with stewardship behavior should be able to persuade qualified faculty members and social community to remain attach in future.

By attaining the standard mentioned before, the university might be more competitive in the education sector. This is because if they are able to meet awareness and expectations of their faculty members and society, with regard to altruistic calling,

wisdom and organizational stewardship. They can better satisfy employees' and students. Therefore, the university should be able to clutch more market share in education sector and expand its branches in whole Pakistan or global in the future.

Suggestions for future research

Future research should focus on emotional healing and persuasive mapping and the influence for different faculty members. In addition, a relative study could be carried out to see the differences in universities among different faculty members in different nations.

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